

Pipeline Length Results Validation

1. Overview

This supplement to the study *Nuclear Winter Could Sever Urban Water Access Across the Northern Hemisphere* details the validation process for the predicted underground water supply network (or, pipeline) lengths, using country-wide reported lengths. The predictions were derived from the population-size-based and street-network-length-based approaches described in the manuscript (subsections 2.4.1 and 2.4.2, respectively), but made for risk-agnostic areas and matched with the closest available datasets required for the corresponding calculations. Validation metrics included R^2 of logged values and Root Mean Squared Logarithmic Error (RMSLE), supplemented by bootstrapping to assess metric consistency. The street-network-length-based predictions outperformed the population-size-based ones in both statistical tests, with an R^2 of 0.78 and an RMSLE of 0.36 compared with R^2 of 0.26 and RMSLE of 0.67, with the bootstrapping confirming the reliability of the metrics.

2. Method

For validation of the predicting performance of the population-size-based and street-network-length-based approaches, we utilized reported water supply network lengths. They are collected in the supplementary material S1. As the reported lengths were country-wide, i.e. non-urban-area parts of the infrastructure were likely to contribute to the value, we predicted lengths for all – not only at-risk – urban areas of each country, and then compared the predictions against the reports.

Given that sources reporting pipeline lengths as of 2024 would not be available yet, we had to use earlier ones and, consequently, predict the historical lengths using both approaches, for the corresponding as-of years. This process had to account for the fact that datasets employed for determining the at-risk urban area, population size, and street network length were unavailable for each year. The current length predictions relied on the latest available versions, i.e. GAIA as of 2018 (Gong et al., 2020), NTL as of 2020 (Zhao et al., 2022), LandScan as of 2023 (Lebakula et al., 2024), and OpenStreetMap as of 2024 (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2024), but, of these, only NTL and LandScan had yearly versions, and OpenStreetMap was limited to the aforementioned one. Thus, we defaulted to searching for the reported value as of 2018 per each country, and matching it with the closest yet latest available datasets. When not found, reported length as of the previous year was sought, with a corresponding shift in the datasets; and so on. E.g. for 2017 ones, we predicted

historical lengths using GAIA as of 2018, NTL and LandScan as of 2017, and OpenStreetMap as of 2024. We devised this method after considering a general infrastructure–population relationship, and assuming the former’s increase rather taking place as an answer to an increase in the latter¹. The supplementary material S1 specifies the as-of years of a country’s reported length and of the datasets applied for the corresponding prediction.

To increase accuracy of the reported data, for a given country, we prioritized the sources authored by the following entities, in a descending order: statistical agencies, other governmental bodies, international organizations, water companies, professional associations (including those comprising water companies), and academics. For reference purposes, author types are specified in the supplementary material S1. In general, the existence of a work in English was checked before looking for one in the country’s official language.

In some cases, we had to calculate the reported length, by summing up such values either of a country’s regions (after acquiring information about the water industry organizational structure of the corresponding period), or of its pipeline constituents. All such operations and their breakdowns are specified in the supplementary material S1.

Due to the largely different scales between the relevant infrastructures of countries, we compared the logged values of the predicted lengths against the logged values of the reported ones to arrive at the R^2 of logged values of both approaches, separately. In order to better understand how close each prediction was to the corresponding report, we were also interested in determining the RMSE. Similar to the R^2 case, we kept in mind the largely scale differences between countries’ infrastructure, and thus calculated the logged values of the predicted lengths against the logged values of the reported ones, essentially obtaining the root mean squared logged error (*RMSLE*).

As it was difficult² to complete the collection of country-wide underground water supply network lengths, additional testing was required to assert confidence that our limited sample (of 34 out of 92 at-risk countries, plus an additional 3 territories³) is likely to be representative of the remaining

¹ The reverse relationship might also be true, but the influence is presumably more subtle, if any.

² Our process of collecting the reported lengths turned out much more time-consuming than previously assumed, due to numerous cases of in-resource terminological ambiguity, missing regional data points, incomplete information about the water industry organizational structure, lack of resources in English, and other issues. Given the difficulties, we ended up with the results validation sample and process as described in section 2. Method. Notably, we found the length reported in the corresponding statistical agency’s works only in 15 out of 40 cases.

³ All methods employed in this study utilized the designation of country boundaries as determined in the dataset Admin 0 – Countries (Natural Earth, 2022), with unique countries being designated as separate sovereign states. This resulted in the 92 at-risk countries. Reported water supply network lengths were also found for 4 additional territories (Hong Kong, Macao, Isle of Man, and Palestine – West Bank). The first 3 of these were included in the results validation sample by utilizing the administrative boundaries of these subregions in the Natural Earth dataset. Palestine – West Bank was excluded for the validation due

countries. For meeting this requirement, we employed bootstrapping to assess the consistency of the R^2 and $RMSLE$ values for the relationship between predicted and reported lengths. The process involved repeatedly sampling our set of both types of lengths (with replacement) to create multiple bootstrap samples, each of the same size as the total set (Booth et al., 1994; Davison and Hinkley, 1997). For each bootstrap sample, the R^2 and $RMSLE$ values were calculated and stored. This procedure was repeated 100,000 times each for both predictive approaches, to generate two distributions of the R^2 and $RMSLE$ values. These distributions were then used to compute the variance and 95% confidence intervals, adjusted by a finite population correction (Nane and Kooijman, 2018), providing an estimate of the variability and reliability of the R^2 and $RMSLE$ metrics.

3. Results and Discussion

The log of the street-network-length-based predictions, when compared with the log of the reported data, have a resulting R^2 value of 0.78. The population-size-based ones, on the other hand, have a significantly poorer R^2 value, of 0.26. In the $RMSLE$ test, the former predictions score 0.36, while the latter ones score a poorer 0.67.

Fig. S3.1. Log of reported lengths vs. log of predicted lengths, for the street-network-length-based and population-size-based predictions.

incomplete reported length data capturing the entirety of Palestine (i.e. the Gaza Strip), but the value is included in the supplementary material S1 regardless of the incompleteness.

Predictions Type	R ² of Logged Values	RMSLE
Street-network-length-based	0.63, 0.89	0.26, 0.43
Population-sized-based	-0.16, 0.56	0.60, 0.73

Table S3.1. 95% confidence intervals of bootstrapping test.

Fig. S3.2. Histogram of R² values for bootstrapping test of logged reported lengths vs. logged predicted lengths, comparing the street-network-length-based and population-size-based predictions.

Fig. S3.3. Histogram of RMSLE values for bootstrapping test of logged reported lengths vs. logged predicted lengths, comparing the street-network-length-based and population-size-based predictions.

The resulting short ranges of high confidence intervals for R^2 and low ones for $RMSLE$, alongside the produced histogram of results, demonstrate that we can be reasonably confident that both metrics for the street-network-length-based predictions are unlikely to change even if additional countries are added. The population-sized-based ones also have a short range of confidence intervals for the $RMSLE$ value, but not for the R^2 , which tends to fluctuate more heavily between runs.

Given the results, we assume the difference between the predicted pipeline lengths from this approach and the corresponding reported ones, besides the reported ones potentially being located outside the urban areas, might stem from incomplete data used to identify said areas. Although also possible to be incomplete, we expect the OpenStreetMap "highway" data – encompassing more paths than strictly defined streets – to somewhat compensate for any incompleteness, by better accounting for the consumer endpoints and other parts of the water supply network located below additional types of "street".

4. Limitations and Uncertainties

The limitations and uncertainties of our validation process are as follows:

- The sources containing the reported lengths rarely used *water supply network* or defined the relevant infrastructure. Thus, collecting such lengths relied on synonymy of this term with those assumed to convey said infrastructure in the sources.
- Some reported lengths were already estimates, or had to be calculated on our end. In such cases, the results depended on the available information on the country's water industry organizational structure of the specific period, or on the multiple in-source terms being synonymous with pipeline constituents.
- Due to lack of yearly versioning of some datasets, those used for predicting pipeline lengths neither were as of the same year nor fully matched the as-of year of the corresponding reported lengths. In order to mitigate the issue, we employed a more complex arrangement of predicting with the datasets closest to the reported as-of years, but prioritizing the latest versions if there was a tie. We also assumed that no significant change occurred in between the corresponding as-of years.
- We only found three sources that explicitly provided length of consumer endpoints of pipelines (European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment, 2015; VKR - Verband Kunststoff-Rohre und -Rohrleitungsteile et al., 2019; Water UK, 2022), of which only the first two met our validation criteria and were used in that manner. Given the third one pointing to suppliers' limited knowledge about the length of the property owners' parts of such endpoints, and the aforementioned rare provision of infrastructure definitions in sources in general, we are highly uncertain how well such constituents were reflected in the reported lengths. With analogous reservations about the predicted ones, as informed in this section's namesake in the manuscript, we are similarly uncertain how the consumer endpoints affected the validation results.

Through the development of this study, and as further discussed in this supplementary material, we have found that many countries either lack comprehensive data on their own water supply networks or do not share the data publicly. Given the critical role of water infrastructure in disaster resilience, we recommend that governments prioritize both the collection and open accessibility of up-to-date pipeline data.

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